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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

MORPHOLOGICAL PROCESS OF COMPOUNDING IN BURA LANGUAGE

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Abstract

Considering the existing fact that every language uses words that exist not on their own but are being created by speakers, Bura language thus is not exceptional; it is observed that the morphological process of compounding exists in Bura language, though, having some identifiable uniqueness which is overt. Therefore, this study set to focus on the morphological process of compounding to determine its operation in the chosen language. The data for this study were collected primarily from 18 Bura native speakers in Biu, Hawul, Garkide and Kwayakusar Local Governments of Borno State, whose ages ranges from 45-75. The data were analysed to ascertain the operational implication of compounding as a morphological process, hence, the study used Item and Process Theory. It found out that the morphological process of compounding exists in Bura and its unique form, even though it shares some identical boundaries with some languages; English to be precise.

Keywords: Morphological, Process, Compounding, Bura, Language.

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INTRODUCTION

Language is an essential means of relating feelings and ideas to other individuals. It is a tool for the functioning of every human society and an institution through which humans communicate and interact with one another using habitually used oral-auditory arbitrary symbols (Hall, 1964). Sapir also asserts that language is a purely human and non-instinctive method of communicating ideas, emotions, and desires using voluntarily produced symbols that are auditory and produced by the organs of speech (1921). This further explains why Bloch and Tragger (5), cited in Lyons (2002), postulate that 'language is a system of arbitrary vocal symbols using which a social group cooperates'. This however views language as more concerned with the social function and pays little or no attention to the communicative function. To Cruttenden, language "is a system of conventional signals used for communication by a whole community. This pattern of conventions covers a system of significant sound units (the phonemes), the inflexion and arrangement of 'words' [MORPHOLOGY and SYNTAX], and association of meaning with words [Semantics]" (2001).

English, as one of the natural languages, has properties for its description. These properties among others include grammatical, phonological, and semantic properties. The grammatical properties are described as mechanisms by which language works when we communicate with other people (Leech and Svartvik 1977). According to them, grammar is a set of abstract rules that enable us to understand how language works. They further argue that these rules, because they are abstract, reside in the human mind and are only manifested through human communication. Thus, it is these rules that usually determine speakers' utterances as being grammatical or ungrammatical.

Furthermore, grammar, as an aspect of language, deals with the study of the relationship between words in a sentence (Egbe 2005). This view sees grammar as the interplay between the various structures that constitute a sentence. This follows however that every sentence is made up of structures (i.e lexical and syntactic structures) and each structure is important for the understanding of the sentence. Thus grammar provides a platform in which the internal structures or constituents of sentences are studied and understood. It gives a practical description of the various structures of sentences which in turn enables the speakers and learners of a particular language to effectively account for all the grammatical sequences and rule out the ungrammatical ones. In a nutshell, grammar deals with the internal linguistic knowledge which operates in the production and recognition of appropriately structured expressions in a particular language.

Brief Historical and Linguistic Background of Bura People

According to Mu'azu and Balami (2010), this history is based on oral tradition because there is no documented book about the earlier history and migration of Bura people to their present-day abode in Nigeria. According to oral traditions, the Bura people claim descendants from Yemen in the Middle East. After migrating from North Africa to the Chad Basin area around 500A.D, they

later moved to Kanem Borno and finally settled on the Biu plateau, which is their present-day location in Nigeria. Some of the reasons for their movement are locust swarms, drought and flood. In this location, they are sparsely distributed and do not have a central government, they are organized into clans. Clan means a name borne by a group of people who have common ancestral fathers. Furthermore, they state that another oral tradition on the origin of the Bura clan states that Sakwa in Bura land was the first to be found. The founders called their clan "NkwarSakwa"; founders of the Biu clan call themselves Mibwala Marama is where the Dibals and Bassi clans are found and Walama are found in Garkidha while those that remained in Shani were being referred to as NkwarShani. These names remain the same up till today. Davies (2016) claims that the Paber (or Babur) are the minority speakers compared to Bura(majority) speakers; the Paber are said to be descendants conquered from YamtarWala. YamtarWala attacked the North of Biu around the 16th century. The few people Yamta brought with him intermarried with the Bura and built up the Biu dynasty into a kingdom. Those who descended from Yamta's group were called Paber (Babur). This is why the Paber and Bura differ considerably in culture and appearance. Although the Bura and Paber speak the same language; they saw themselves as different ethnic groups. The Bura is referred to as the majority of native speakers who live in the mountainous regions surrounding the Biu plateau, an area that covers Southern Borno.

Mu'azu and Balami (2010) state that the word "Bura" refers to the kingdom, the people as well as the language. He also mentions that Bura native speakers are referred to as "Babur- Bura". The language is similar to Kilba, Marghi and Higgi. In other words, Bura is an integrated union of many kin ethnic dialects like Marghi, Chibok, Fali, Higgi and Kilba. The Bura, Marghi and Kilba are believed to be the earliest linguistic groups that migrated from North-East Africa into their present areas in Nigeria; they are the Chadic languages that descended from a single ancestral language, which can be referred to as proto-Chadic (Greenberg 1996). Proto Chadic itself, along with other Proto languages belong to a family of languages, whose ancestry dates to a much earlier time The phylum is called the Afro-Asiatic.

Morphology: An Overview

Morphology is defined by Mathews (2000) as that branch of linguistics that is concerned with the "forms and words" in different uses and constructions. He further says that morphology is a branch of linguistics that is concerned with the structure of words; their internal structure and the changes they undergo when altered to form new words.

In a similar vein, Nida (1974) defines morphology as the study of morphemes and their arrangements informing words. Morphemes are the minimal meaningful units that may constitute words or parts of words. Examples are: *re-*, *de-*, *un-*, *ish-*, *ly-*, in the combinations *rearrange*, *decompose*, *untie*, *boyish* and *lovely*. The morpheme arrangement treated under the morphology of

a language includes all combinations that form words or parts of words.

Haspelmath (2002) defines morphology as the study of systematic co-variation in the form and meaning of words, and the combination of morphemes to yield words. He mentions two morphological rules; morpheme-based model and word-based model. In the morpheme-based model, morphological rules are taught as combined morphemes to come up with another word in much the same way as systematic rules combine words. Different combinations of morphemes are used to form words.

Tomori (1977) defines morphology as the study of the structure of the word-the study of the rule governing the formation of a word in a language.

The morpheme has been defined as the smallest unit of a word that has semantic or grammatical meaning. Morphemes are the different building blocks that make up a complex word. Morphemes are categorised into two: free and bound morphemes. A free morpheme can stand alone as an independent word in a phrase, such as a hand, ball. Etc a bound morpheme cannot stand alone but must be attached to another morpheme certain bound morphemes are known as affixes, for example, 's' 'ed' 'able' 'al'.

The root is a morpheme that appears to be the core of a word while some other appears to be an addition or appendix; therefore the root is considered to be very hard of the word. For example, in the word *stabilize* the heart of the word is *stable*; this is the core or the root morpheme, and *-size* is a dependent morpheme.

The stem of a word is that part of the word to which the last morpheme in the word is structurally added. For example in the word *naturalization*, the stem is *naturalized* and the last morpheme structurally added to it *-action*. *Nature* is the root of the whole word, it is also the stem to which *-al* is appended to derive *natural*. It follows therefore that roots can also be a stem and a can also be a root. In other words, all roots can be stem but not all stems are roots, as shown in the above example.

According to Tomori (1977), there are two commonest morphological types in English which are the additive and replacive morphemes. The additive morphemes are added to roots or to words such as *achieve* → *achievement*., while in replacive, one sound replaces another: for example in food/feet, the vowel sound /i:/ replaces the sound /u/ in the plural form of the word.

Bauer (1983) defines morphology as a sub-branch of linguistics that deals with the internal structure of words; and that the basic units of analysis recognised in morphology are morphemes. He defines morphemes as the minimal unit of grammatical analysis; each unit has its form, meaning and distribution. For example, the word *unfriendly* can be segmented to show its constituent elements thus: 'un' 'friend' and 'ly'. The form 'un'-prefixes has a meaning of negation; a *friend* is the root of the word and '-ly' is an adjectival suffix.

According to Bauer (1983), morphemes are abstract elements of analysis that occur in autographic phonetic forms which realize the morphemes. In the morphology of English, morphemes are attached to roots, stems and bases by inflectional and derivational means. He describes the 'root' as a form that is not

further analysable; it is that part of a word that remains when all inflectional and derivational affixes have been removed, that is, it is indivisible. For example, in the word *untouchable* when 'un' and 'able' are removed 'touch' is the root of the word.

Moreover, Bauer (1983) discusses morphological processes to consist of *derivational* and *inflectional* processes. According to him, the derivational is closer to the root than inflectional. It involves many variables in an open system: re- un- nes, dis -en, etc while inflectional deals purely with grammatical morphology. It involves a few variables in a close system; ed, s, en, est, er, ing, es. It produces word forms of a single lexeme (word) and is semantically regular, and it doesn't change the word –class of a word. For example;

Root:	Inflected:
a. care	cars
b. bucket	buckets

Furthermore, Bauer (1983) says that apart from derivational and inflectional morphology, there is what is called compounding. He explains compounding as the formation of a new lexicon from two or more potential stems that have not been subjected to a derivational process. For example:

Walking + stick → walking stick

Dining + table → dining table

In his view, Radford (2004) says morphological evidence comes from the inflectional and derivational properties of the word. According to him, the inflectional properties relate to different forms of the same words. For example, the plural forms of nouns like a window, school, chair, are formed by adding the plural inflexion ' -s' to give, for example, windows, schools, and chairs etc.

In a similar view, Plag (2003) states that inflectional morphemes encode grammatical categories such as plural (workers), person (works), tens (picked) or case (Ali's). There is no inflectional prefix in English; inflectional morphemes always occur outside derivational morphemes and do not change the grammatical categories of the base word. A plural marker on a noun does not change the category, nor does the past-tense marker on the verb.

Also, Scalise (1986) states that inflectional morphemes always follow the element to which they are attached and do not change the syntactic category of their based and cannot be attached to stems. Example of inflectional rules:

(girl) N + s) N

(talk) V + ed) V

The Concept of Compounding

Matthews (2000) categorizes morphology into two i.e lexical morphology and inflectional morphology. He further divides lexical morphology into compounding and derivation. In the case of compounding, Matthews further

states that compounding/compound formation occurs in a situation whereby two independent words are put together to form another word which when examined or split into two, the meaning is the sum of the words that -made it -up. Also, Rufai (79), cited in Mu'azu (2009), states that compounding consists of a determinant and the determinant is the determining element; therefore it precedes the determination. Bauer (83) says that apart from derivational and inflectional morphology, there is what is called compounding. He explains compounding as the formation of a new lexicon from two or more potential stems that have not been subjected to a derivational process.

Kayode (2015) defines compounding as a morphological process where two free morphemes are joined together to form a word. It is the joining of two separate words to produce a single form. In the same vein, Fannami and Muazu (2012) state that compounding as a word-formation process occupies a prominent place in the language word-formation system. It refers to the process of joining two or more formerly independent lexical morphemes (root) to form a single lexeme (word). Compounding is a common word formation process (Libben, 20), but different languages make use of compounding to different levels.

Haspelmath (2002) asserts that compounding is a complex lexeme that can be thought of as consisting of two or more base lexemes. In the simplest case, a compound consists of two that are joined together (called compound number). Umar (1997) asserts that in English, new words can be formed from already existing words by a process known as compounding. This is a process in which individual words are joined together to form a compound word.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework adopted for this study is Item and Process Theory.

Hockett, in the year 1954, had also raised an issue on the choice between two competing approaches to morphological description: item-and-arrangement and item-and-process. Both theories are associated with American structuralist-linguistics, codified by Bloomfield (1933) (see Aronoff and Fudeman 2011). Also known as the morpheme-based morphological theory, item-and-arrangement looks at a set of morphemes put after each other in a sequential order like beads on a string. To understand this in another way, the theory considers the techniques for breaking words down into separate morphemes, which are the said items Morphology is then seen to be concerned with the arrangement of these items (the morphemes) into a particular order to realize a particular structure. For example, Faithfulness results from the line-up of the three morphemes thus: faith+ful+ness. But there is no special reason to expect affixation to be the only operation in morphology, even though it is predominate. It is a fact well known that the morphology of natural languages employs several other processes, among others, like blending reduplication, or compounding, as it concerns our study, in the formation of words.

We, therefore, chose to go with the lexeme-based theory, which we had

earlier referred to like the Item and-Process, rather than the morphological approach that was based on the concatenation of morphological items. In our adopted theory of Item-and Process, complex words are considered to be the result of the operation of processes on similar words.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The data were collected from Biu, Hawul, Garkide and Kwayakusar Local Governments of Borno State and the sample selection procedure is made up of 18 Bura native speakers comprising of men and women, whose age ranges between 45-75years; the informants were selected from these average because the researcher believes that their language is unadulterated and being the fact that they are native speakers, they are competent of their language. Our informants were therefore drawn from different occupational backgrounds Out of the 18 informants selected and interviewed (5) farmers, (5) school teachers, (3) retired civil servants and the remaining (5) are market women.

To arrive at a reliable collection of data, the researcher employed both the primary and secondary methods of data collection. The primary method involved the collection of data using the structured and unstructured interviews of informants i.e. native speakers of the Bura language.

The researcher, being not so fluent in the Bura language, employed the use of code-mixing, where the Hausa language was employed as an instrument to interact with informants in cases where there was a communication gap.

The researcher introduced a few compounded words which were much familiar to informants such as "*asiràzi*" meaning come here, "*kùnrntàkù*" (bushmeat) etc., which gave informants an idea of compounding and what the researcher sourced for. The informants willingly contributed their quota giving the researcher a list of Bura compounds used in their everyday conversation, some of the informants who were literates translated from Bura language to the English language while the researcher had to play her role translating and arranging the data based on their grammatical categories for adequate data presentation and analysis.

The secondary source of data collection for this research is a library where relevant text extracted from books were used which supplements the primary source.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Sample A

Bura Noun Based Compounds

Bura noun-based compound have nouns as the core components; it could have the following examples:

Noun+ Noun (N+N)

This is a category of the compound is the summation of two nouns; the meaning corresponds with the lexical items joined together. The two languages

here share some identical features in the formation of this category. Examples:

Noun + Noun

- a) kùhyì + di
“chief” “village”
b) nkwar ±—maya
“daughter” “mother”
c) mâfa + nkwa
“slave” “girl”
d) kùhyì + mwàla
“king” “wife”
e) kùta + mbwà
“belly” . “house”

Compounds

- kùhyirdi
“village chief”
nkwarmaya
“sister”
màfar nkwa
“slavegirl”
mwàlakùhyì
“queen”
kùtàmbwà
“inner room”

Worthy to note here is that some Bura compound structures, when translated into English, would reveal unacceptable structures (see example a).

Sample B Noun+Verb(N+V)

This category is the summation of a noun and verb; the compound is a noun, whereby the lexical item and the compound correspond together. Examples:

Noun + Verb

- a) mbwa + pi
“house” “sleep”
b) mndr + hela
“person” “steal”
c) mbwa + adú’à
“house” “prayer”
d) mndər + kidà
“person” “beg”
e) kər. + kəta
“head” “ache”

Compounds

- mbwarpì
“bedroom”
mndərheəla
“thief”
mbwàraclú’à
“church”
nrndərkida
“begger”
kərkəta
“headache”

It is pertinent to note here that the two languages here differ in that Bura compounds do not maintain their compound structures when translated to English (see examples b to d).

Sample C**Noun + Conjunction (ka) + Noun.**

Here, the summation involves a noun(number), a conjunctive linker (“kà” in Bura, “and”) and another noun which results to the actual number. Examples:

Noun + Conjunction (kà)+noun

- a) sùrkùrnàrì + kà + màkr

Compounds

- sùrkùrnàrì- kà-rnàkr

"twenty" "and" "three"
 b) sùrkùmàrì + kà + ntúfú
 "twenty" "and" "five"
 c) màlomàrì + kà + kwà
 "thirty" "and" "six"
 d) màkùmàd + kà + úmthlà
 "thirty" "and" "nine"
 e) nfwàrkùmàrì + kà + ntúfú
 forty" "and" "five"

"twenty three"
 sùrkùmàrì- kà-ntúfú
 "twenty-five"
 màkùmàrì-kà-kwà
 "thirty-six"
 màkùmàrì-kà-úmthlà
 "thirty-nine"
 nfwàrkùmàrì
 "fourty-five"

It is evident in the category above that the combination is exceptional in the English, unlike what can be equated in the Bura language which uses a conjunctive linker.

Noun + Adjective (N + A)

This category is made up a noun and an adjective; the compound is usually an adjective or a noun. For example;

Noun + Adjective

a) nmdər + didi
 "man" "dirty"
 b) kràthlú + jáng
 "chest" "cold"

Compounds

mndərdidi
 "dirty man"
 jáhgkràthlu .
 "pneumonia"

Bura Verb Based Compounds

Bura verb-based compound is a category of compounds made up of verbs as the core component; it has the structure verb + verb, verb + noun, verb + preposition, verb + adverb respectively.

Verb + Verb (V+ V)

The category is the summation of verbs; the result is also a verb, where the result corresponds with the two lexical items joined. Example:

Verb + Verb

a) hara + hangkal
 "take" "care"

Compound

harahangkal
 "take care/be careful"

Verb + Noun (V + N)

This category involves the summation of a verb and a noun; the meaning reflects thelexical items joined together. For example:

Verb + Noun

a) kúbar + nfwà
 "meet" "tree"

Compounds

kúḅarnfwà
 "forest"

b) Kà + súcfa	kàsúcfa
“have” “two”	“double”
c) Kà + kúrákú	kákúrákú
“have” “voice”	“loud”
d) Ká + amfani	káamfani
“have” “benefit”	“useful”
e) bù + tsì	bùtsì
“stike” “hand”	“applaud”

Cardinal to note here is that all the exemplified Bura compound structures above converted to English give the sense of single words.

Verb + Preposition (V + Prep.)

This category is the summation of a verb and preposition; the compound is usually a verb. Examples:

a) thiata + cimta	tháta
“wake” “up”	“wake”

Verb + Adverb (V+ Adv.)

This category is the summation of a verb and adverb; the compound corresponds with the two lexical items joined together. Examples:

Verb + Adverb	Compounds
asirà + azì	asìrazì
“come” “here”	“come here”

Bura Adjectival Based Compounds

Bura adjectival based compounds have the adjective as the core; they have the structure of adjective + noun respectively.

Adjective + Noun (A + N)

This category is a summation of an adjective and a noun; the meaning is usually a noun, whereby the meaning corresponds with the lexical items joined together. Most of what is evident between the languages here are that they tend to reveal similarities in their respective formations. For examples:

Adjective + Noun	Compounds
a) biliri + mva	bilin-mva
“new” “year”	“newyear”
b) hala + mwáta	mwáta-hala
“old” “car”	“oldcar”
c) mapu + md	mapù-md
“white” “man”	“whiteman”
d) mìcìka + ncá	mìcìka-ncá

“blinked eye” “eye”

e) úlà + mdə

dry” “person”

“a blinked eye”

ú1à-mdə

“an emaciated person”

Numerical Compound Adjectives

They are adjectives that have the structure of numerical adjectival compounds. The numerical compound in the Bura language is formed through a complete reduplication process of the numeral. For examples:

Base Form

a) pál

“one”

b) úmthlá

“nine”

e) kúma

“ten”

d) aru

“One hundred”

Compound Adjective

pál-pál

“one each”

úmthlá-úrnhlá

“nine each”

kúpma-kúma .

“ten each”

aru-aru

“one-hundred-each”

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher was able to identify the various compounds that occur in the Bura language. The study discovered compounds like noun based compounds, verb-based compounds and adjectival based compounds. It is pertinent to note that Bura compounds have similarities and dissimilarities with English compounds to some extent. Bura and English languages both categorize compounds into their grammatical categories as noun-based compounds and adjectival based compounds, among others respectively.

The noun-based compounds have been classified into different grammatical categories of noun + noun. (n + n), noun + verb (n +v), noun + conjunction + noun and noun+ adjective (n +a). The verb based compounds includes verb + verb (v + v), verb + noun (v + n), verb + preposition (v + p), and verb + adverb (v+a). The adjectival based compounds consist of adjective + noun (a +n). We also have compound adjectives which consist of color adjectives and numerical adjectival compounds.

The study also found that some Bura compound structures, when translated to English, reveal the grammatical sense of single words; hence they change from being compound words.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Bura compound formation analysis, being an aspect of morphology, requires relevant compound words, which are quite uneasy due to lack of available materials, and most of which when converted to English do not maintain their compound structures. We hope that our findings would serve as a

base for other researchers to develop more interest in the study of different aspects of Bura morphology.

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